

NANOFIBRE COMPOSITES FROM CAPRINE BIOMASS

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ABSTRACT

The demand of milk, meat and other livestock products increases every year due to population growth, urbanization and increasing income in developing countries. This results in a significant increase in animal waste/manure and feed residues. In order to promote environmental sustainability, new uses of livestock waste are pursued. Ruminants only convert about 50 % of the consumed feed to energy and the remains are excreted. Therefore, the waste of these animals contains still a significant amount of fibrous materials originating from their feed. Making use of this waste stream and turning manure into applicable materials was thus envisaged in this study.

Goat manure was used as raw material. After thorough purification involving chemical and mechanical treatments, fibres, micro- and nanofibrillated cellulose with various surface properties, were isolated. The micro and nanofibrillated cellulose obtained were used to produce papers. These papers were characterised with respect to their physical and mechanical properties in order to assess the potential of these fibres as reinforcement for polymers. Composites were manufactured by forming fibre preforms followed by compression moulding. The influence of the chemical composition of the fibres on composite properties was investigated. The thermal and mechanical properties of the produced animal waste composites will also be discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is one of the most abundant naturally occurring reproducible organic compounds. It is one of the major components in at least a third of advanced plants. Around 40 % of dry wood and more than 90 % of raw cotton and flax consist of cellulose. Since the 1800s cellulose has also been a major interest in the scientific world [1]. Grass, for example, which is the primary food for livestock contains approximately 30 to 60 % cellulose [2, 3]. The number of livestock increased 2011 in comparison to 2010 by 1.5% [4] resulting in a significant increase of waste generated [5]. Approximately 88 million tons of manure are produced annually in the UK alone [5]. The high amount of waste generated brings forth the question on how these wastes are being disposed or utilized. Affordable alternatives for handling animal

waste other than agricultural application should be considered in order to achieve efficiency. The under-utilization of ruminant manure together with the significant amount of animal waste generated each year leads to the need of establishing a better and more sustainable waste management system. An attractive alternative to land disposal is to change manure into a bio resource for value added products. With a fibre content of approximately 30 to 60 % [6], the prospect to produce value added products from agricultural animal manure is very promising.

In this work we demonstrate the feasibility of producing paper from caprine waste. We investigated the fibre content of treated manure pulp (TMP), as the amount of fibres in the nanopaper will indicate whether the material can be appropriately be used as reinforcement. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of papers produced from TMP were assessed, optimizing the amount of bleaching agent required. Ultimately, composites produced from animal manure papers and PP were manufactured and tested regarding their mechanical performance.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Goat manure was collected randomly at a free range farm in Greece and dried overnight at 120°C prior to treatment by using a convection oven. 15% sodium hypochlorite solution, sodium hydroxide obtained from Sigma Aldrich. All materials were used as received without further purification.

2.2 Manure pretreatment and pulping

Dried manure (20 g) was suspended in 500 mL water and disintegrated at 20000 rpm using a laboratory blender (Waring Blender LB20EG, Christison Particle Technologies, Gateshead, UK). This suspension was centrifuged twice at 9700 rpm to remove excess water. Further treatment was conducted by redispersing the centrifuged manure in deionized water (4 L). Sodium hydroxide (4 g L⁻¹) was added to the mixture which was then heated to 80 °C for 20 min under stirring to remove any remaining microorganisms and soluble polysaccharides. The treated manure (TM) was then successively centrifuged and homogenised to neutral pH with successive washing.

In order to remove lignin, the treated manure was first dispersed in 1.5 L water and 150 mL 10 % sodium hypochlorite was added to the mixture under stirring. The mixture was left overnight followed by centrifugation in order to remove excess bleach. The treated manure pulp (TMP) was stored at 4 °C prior to analysis.

2.3 Papermaking process

Papers with a grammage of 250 g m⁻² were prepared by dispersing never dried TMP in deionized water and vacuum filtered until a uniform cake was obtained. The cake was pressed at 120 °C for 2 hours under a weight of 3 kg.

2.4 TMP-PP composite

Never dried TMP, treated with 0.4% sodium hypochlorite, was dispersed in deionized water and PP fibres were added to this suspension. The volume fraction of the never dried TMP ranged from 20 to 60 %. The suspension was left overnight to promote better homogeneity. Afterwards, the suspension of TMP and PP were vacuum filtered until a uniform cake was obtained. The obtained cake was pressed at 1.5 Tonne and 120 °C for 1 hour, followed by 15 minutes at 175°C. The final composite, was left for 1 hour at 120°C to complete the hornification reaction achieving a final grammage of 1000 g m⁻².

2.4 Characterisation of manure paper

2.4.1 Scanning Electron Microscopy

SEM images for displaying the difference between treated and untreated manure samples were obtained using a high-resolution field emission gun scanning electron microscope (LEO Gemini 1525 FEG-SEM, Oberkochen, Germany). The accelerating voltage used was 5 kV. Prior to SEM, the samples were mounted to SEM stubs using carbon tabs and coated with Cr (K550 sputter coater, Emitech Ltd, Ashford, Kent, UK) for 1 min at 75 mA.

2.4.2 Mechanical testing

TMP papers were cut into rectangular specimens using a paper cutter. The samples had an overall length of 75 mm, an average thickness of 0.1 mm and a width of 15 mm. Tensile tests were conducted in accordance to BS EN ISO 1924-2:2008 using an universal testing machine (Instron 5969, Instron GmbH, Germany). The testing speed was 1 mm/min with a 1 kN load cell and a gauge length of 50 mm.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Goat manure was collected at a Greek farm, dried and alkaline treated to remove microorganisms. As shown in Figure 1, untreated manure contains various cells and minerals other than undigested fibres. These materials were removed primarily with washing, sieving and treatment with sodium hydroxide.

Figure 1: SEM images of raw manure.

After this treatment, only the undigested fibres remained, mainly consisting of cellulose and lignins. It is known that lignin hinders the formation of hydrogen bonds thus reducing the possibility of hornification. This is due to the bulky structure of lignin, which reduces the number of contact points between cellulosic OH-bonds reducing the possibility of forming hydrogen bonds. The removal of lignin was also crucial as it is responsible for the brown colour of the paper. It was observed that TMP is yellowish in colour and slightly transparent, whereas TM is opaque and brown. Thus, by adding more sodium hypochlorite into the treatment system, the paper became lighter.

Papers from this treated manure (TM) were produced. Moreover, TM was treated with varying amounts of sodium hypochlorite to yield treated manure pulp (TMP), which was subsequently manufactured into papers as well. The mechanical performance of these papers was evaluated by tensile tests.

The results of mechanical testing of TMP papers in tensile mode are shown in Table 1. The tensile strength is defined as the maximum load required to break the sample per unit area of the specimen (15 mm width). In the case of TM, no tensile properties could be established as the papers made from that material were too loose to be analysed. This was due to the presence of lignin in the samples that hindered hornification of the papers during manufacture. Accordingly, for further tests, delignification of manure pulp was performed through the treatment with sodium hypochlorite [7].

Table 1: Tensile properties of treated manure samples

Sample	Tensile Modulus	Tensile Strength
TM	Not measurable	Not measurable
TMP	1.77 ± 0.18 GPa	12.14 ± 1.05 MPa

TM suspensions (1L) were treated with 10 to 70 mL of sodium hypochlorite. We found that with increasing amounts of the bleaching agent the modulus decreased as shown in Figure 2. However, for the tensile strength a maximum at 0.4% bleach used during treatment was found. For higher amounts, 50 mL and above, the tensile strength decreased again. This was because excess amount of bleach led to the deformation of cellulosic bonds, thus reducing hornification during hot pressing. However, no paper could be made using only 10 mL sodium hypochlorite. The reason for this is similar to the one for TM samples, in which the presence of lignin hindered the formation of hydrogen bonds during hot pressing. Thus no paper could be produced. Based on these results, 0.4% sodium hypochlorite was chosen as optimum bleaching agent amount for the chemical treatment of TMP and was used subsequently for the production of TMP-Polypropylene composites.

Figure 2: Tensile properties of TMP with different amounts of bleaching agent.

After optimization of the amount of sodium hypochlorite used during treatment 40 mL to obtain the best fibre preforms, a batch of TMP was prepared to be used as reinforcement in Polypropylene (PP) composites. The composites were prepared by co-filtering a mixture of PP fibres and TMP with different volume fractions. We found that addition of TMP into the PP composite system significantly lowered the tensile strength of the composite (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Tensile properties of TMP-PP composites with different TMP volume fraction.

However, the modulus of the TMP-PP composites was slightly higher compared to neat PP. This may be due to the lack of bonding between TMP fibres and PP, as shown in Figure 4(a). From the SEM image it can be clearly perceived that TMP did not bind to the PP fibre melt. Further investigation also shows that the TMP-PP composite contains pores which further decreased the tensile properties of the composite (Figure 4(b)). These pores were formed due to the presence of water in the fibre cake during the curing process due to the lack of bonding between TMP and PP.

Figure 4: Microscopic images of TMP-PP composites

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have successfully produced microfibrillated cellulosic papers from agricultural animal waste. The delignified microfibrillated cellulose paper exhibited up to 10.8 MPa tensile strength, whereas paper rich in lignin had no measurable tensile strength. This implies that removing lignin improved the mechanical properties and the hornification process of microfibrillated cellulose papers. The optimized paper was

subsequently manufactured into composites with PP fibres. While the tensile strength was slightly reduced by the insertion of the animal manure paper, the tensile modulus remained unchanged. However, a material based on animal manure could be produced exhibiting mechanical properties on the level of standard polyolefins from fossil resources. Thus, microfibrillated cellulose produced from agricultural animal manure offers potential as promising value added product derived from agricultural waste streams.

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